

Statistical Adjustment for 'Prevent Defense' When Evaluating Team Performance in Soccer

Andrey Skripnikov*, Ahmet Cemek, David Gillman
Natural Sciences Division, New College of Florida

Abstract

Having looked at the full match statistics for the England-France 2022 FIFA World Cup Quarterfinal, one could come away thinking “England lost despite having played better than France”: 16 to 8 shot attempts, 5 corners to France’s 2, resulting in a 1-2 loss. What’s disregarded is the scoring context: in the 40 minutes when the match was tied (0-0, 1-1), France actually led in those statistical categories, while consciously ceding initiative to England in the 66 minutes when up a goal as a tactical choice in order to protect the lead. We use sequenced match event data across five major European club leagues over the past 15 years to study impacts of tactical choices on teams’ offensive outputs during different scoring situations. Moreover, we incorporate other factors hypothesized to affect the likelihood of implementing certain tactics such as red card differential and whether team plays at home or away, while controlling for team levels (via pre-match betting coefficients) and game minute. For that, we leverage modeling approaches tailored towards count response data, prioritizing balance between quality of fit and simplicity. The best model is subsequently utilized for statistical adjustments to teams’ offensive outputs, accounting for the likely tactical choices due to game context.

Keywords. Model Selection, Negative Binomial, Poisson regression, Sports Statistics, Sports Analytics

*Corresponding author

1 Introduction

Soccer, also known as football, is one of the most popular sports in the world. According to the International Federation of Association Football (French: Fédération Internationale de Football Association), 5 billion people have engaged with the FIFA World Cup Qatar 2022 [1]. In soccer, statistics play a crucial role when analyzing various aspects of the game, from player and team performance evaluation to yielding valuable strategic insights. For example, shot attempts and corner kicks could tell a story of which team or player was more proactive throughout the game. Nonetheless, looking at sheer game totals that teams accumulate without specifying the full context under which the events occurred can often lead to misinterpretation.

For instance, upon analyzing the match statistics of the 2022 FIFA World Cup Quarterfinal between England and France, one might conclude that “England lost despite being the *better team*” based on having taken 16 shot attempts to France’s 8, 8 to 5 shots on target, 5 corners to 2, resulting in a 1-2 loss [2]. However, the metrics derived simply from these total shot and corner counts disregard the scoring context: in the 40 minutes when the match was tied (0-0, 1-1), France led in all of the mentioned statistical categories, while consciously ceding initiative to England in the 66 minutes when up a goal as a tactical choice to protect the gained lead. The end goal of our work is to inspect the nature of the effects that the various contextual factors - much like score differential - have on offensive production numbers of a team (e.g. shot attempts and corners), subsequently adjusting these numbers for said factors. Such adjustment could potentially yield a more objective picture of how each team performed within a certain game. In this section we will first introduce some of the previous research and metrics that exist in soccer analytics, along with analogous research questions tackled in other sports. Then we will finish the section by detailing our particular research question and its novelty.

1.1 Previous Research

There are existing metrics and approaches in soccer performance analysis that encompass a range of methodologies aimed at describing game dynamics. The most popular one in modern soccer analytics is the Expected Goal (xG) model [3], which assesses the probability of a shot resulting in a goal based on various factors such as shot location, angle, distance, and type. By assigning a numerical value to the quality of scoring chances, xG models provide a quantitative measure for the quality of shots and opportunities a team generates. Besides pure shot characteristics, some models use other factors such as proxies to quantify psychological effects, like match attendance, match importance and goal differential [4]. Mead et al. suggest that psychological pressure may influence the likelihood of scoring goals, additionally indicating that goal differential was among the most influential variables considered in the expected goals models. With that said, the exact nature of the effect wasn’t studied in detail due to overly complex models with low interpretability (“black box” models). As analogous examples from other sports, American football has Expected Points assigned to each play, which considers game context in evaluating contribution of said play towards scoring (rather than just the play directly resulting in a score) [5]. Lastly, [6] derived an expected value of a possession in rugby based on contextual factors such as field location and nature of preceding possession’s outcome (e.g. opposition error, penalty, goal-line dropout, completed set, etc).

In regards to an explicit statistical adjustment for contextual information in soccer, [7, 8] modeled the dependence between goals scored and allowed by a team in a soccer match using various bivariate distributions. Those papers also incorporated an “offense-defense” model initially intro-

duced in [9] for American football (and later also leveraged by [10] in college basketball), where team’s scoring is assumed to be a function of their offense and opponent’s defense, hereby adjusting for strength of the opposition. As a further extension, [11] worked on American College Football data to adjust several offensive statistical outputs for both the opponent and a subset of players on your own team (“complementary unit”). Lastly, given the importance of home-field advantage [12], all of the models above also incorporated the home factor.

1.2 Research Question

This paper aims to address the limitations of traditional soccer match statistics, such as total shot attempts and corners, that tend to disregard factors related to the tactical context within the game. We used match event sequencing data across five major European leagues over the past 15 years, to study the impacts of tactical choices on the aforementioned statistical categories (shots and corner kicks). In particular, we hypothesized the likelihood of implementing certain tactics to associate with several factors such as the score and red card differential at the time of the event (shot or corner kick), whether the team played at home or away, relative strengths of the teams, and game minute. Prematch betting coefficients were leveraged to gauge how evenly matched the two teams are, which we hypothesized to be an important aspect to control for when estimating the impacts of the aforementioned variables on likelihood of implementing certain tactics. Additionally, we conjectured the game minute to play a role, due to the intuition of trailing teams becoming more desperate (while the leading teams - more cautious) as the game nears the end. We make sure to explicitly test the aforementioned hypotheses via comparing the models that include various permutations of the aforementioned factors, along with various interactions between them. In the end, for the selected model we studied the nature of said impacts and applied a statistical adjustment to account for these contextual factors by projecting each team’s performance onto the same baseline scenario (tied home game with equal number of men), thereby providing new insights into the game dynamics.

Although previous research was conducted on modeling the expected goals (xG) based on a variety of factors, including score differential, our work differs in several critical facets. First, it focuses on other statistical categories such as shots and corner kicks, that also play an important role in evaluating team performance. Second, we leverage contextual factors such as red card differential and also control for potential disparity in team levels (via prematch betting coefficients), neither of which has been done previously to the best of our knowledge. Moreover, our statistical adjustments provide a different insight altogether to that of calculating metrics like xG , with us projecting teams onto a hypothetical shared baseline game scenario when comparing their offensive outputs. Lastly, we also emphasize interpretability of the results, avoiding overly complex, “black box”, types of models and algorithms.

2 Methods

2.1 Data Sources and Preprocessing

Our primary data sources are *ESPN.com* and *Oddsportal.com* websites. We utilized JavaScript to web scrape sequential event data from *ESPN.com* across five major European leagues (English Premier League, Spanish La Liga, German Bundesliga, French Ligue 1, and Italian Serie A) over 2008-2023. It resulted in a massive dataset of minute-by-minute commentary on game events such as shot attempts, shots on goal, goals, corners, yellow and red cards, etc. Additionally, we scraped betting coefficients from *Oddsportal.com* for the same time frame and leagues

to mitigate potential confounding effect arising from team-level differences. Betting coefficients are a good proxy for team strength as they are calculated using a combination of historical data, recent team performance, injuries, expert opinion, and market demand. The dynamic nature of *Oddsportal.com* required use of the browser automation library *Selenium* [13].

With the web scraped text data being largely unstructured, we performed an extensive data wrangling and preprocessing pipeline. It involved things like: text matching via regular expressions (*Regex*) in order to recognize game events and attribute them to teams; properly incorporating stoppage time at the end of halves; matching the *ESPN.com* text commentary with the *Oddsportal.com* data; etc. Lastly, we calculate the win probability differential (*Win.Prob.Diff*) by converting the prematch betting coefficients to win probabilities and subtracting the opponent's win probability from the team's own win probability. For the final data format that was utilized during statistical modeling, we accumulated event totals for each minute for each game, along with the score and red card differential at the time. The goal was to examine the team's per-minute rates of offensive output in shots and corner kicks, while also accounting for home factor, win probability differential and game minute. Note that, to avoid the overlap in game minute value that happens for the extra time of the first half and the first minutes of the second half, we decided to exclude the first half's extra time data from our model estimation, avoiding sample size imbalance it would've caused for game minutes around halftime. Nonetheless, we did make sure to incorporate that data back into our workflow when making statistical adjustments, in order to account for all game events in providing the final projections.

2.2 Statistical Modeling

Due to the count nature of statistics such as shots and corners, we leveraged Poisson distribution [14] as the cornerstone of our modeling approaches. In particular, we considered Poisson Generalized Linear Model (GLM) and its more flexible extension in Negative Binomial GLM [15]. The latter helps deal with the issue of overdispersion, where variance of the response variable (e.g. shots or corners) ends up higher than its mean value. The aforementioned approaches allowed us to model the per-minute rate of offensive production, e.g. shots or corner kicks per minute.

To explain the response variable (e.g. shots) in our regression, we incorporated the following predictors: score differential, red card differential, home indicator, win probability difference and game minute. To allow for non-linear relationships, we implement generalized additive modeling (GAM) [16]. Smoothing splines were used to estimate the potentially non-linear effects of all factors but the binary home indicator, which was represented via a single dummy variable.

2.3 Model Selection and Statistical Adjustments

To carry out the model selection, we proceeded to fit models with an array of feature permutations, comparing everything to the main baseline model that included all the five aforementioned factors - score and red card differential, home factor, win probability differential, and game minute. We used both Akaike and Bayesian Information Criteria (AIC, BIC) to guide us through variable selection, helping address our priority of picking the simplest model possible - hence easy to interpret - while retaining a good fit [17]. In particular, to test the importance of each individual factor, we fit the model with that factor excluded, subsequently comparing it to the baseline. Moreover, to test for any pairwise interactions, we fit models with those interactions included (via two-dimensional smoothing spline) and compared them to the baseline as well.

Once the final model is fitted and the estimates are obtained for the effects of scoring differential,

red card differential and home factor, we proceed to apply the statistical adjustment. If the count for a certain offensive output (e.g. shots) is accumulated during a time period when the score differential is d , $d \neq 0$, then we project it onto a tied game via multiplication by $e^{-(\hat{\eta}_d - \hat{\eta}_0)}$, where $\hat{\eta}_d - \hat{\eta}_0$ represents the difference in estimated linear predictor ($\eta = \log(\text{Shots})$) values between score differential of d and 0. That is simply a reciprocal of what happens to the shot rate when going from tied game to a score differential d (it gets multiplied by $e^{\hat{\eta}_d - \hat{\eta}_0}$). If the shot count is obtained during a time period when the red card differential is r , $r \neq 0$, it's projected onto a game with equal number of red cards via analogous reciprocal multiplication. Note that in the final model there won't be any interaction terms, hence when obtaining linear predictor estimates for different score and red card differentials, one simply needs to make sure that the rest of the predictors are held at the same values for both estimates. Lastly, to project an away team's performance onto a home team hypothetical, we multiply their shots by $e^{-\hat{\gamma}}$, where γ is the dummy variable coefficient for home factor, with home being the baseline category. If offensive outputs were accumulated by a team during a tied home game with zero red card differential, no statistical adjustment is applied.

Notice that no explicit statistical adjustment is applied for win probability differential and game minute. We don't believe it's fair to penalize a team for being inherently better (or vice versa), nor does it make practical sense to enhance/downplay statistics simply based on how early/late in the match the numbers were accumulated. The primary purpose behind including those aspects in the model was mostly to control for them when estimating other factors' effects, such as score differential, red card differential and home factor.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Model Selection and Nature of Estimated Effects

We fit regular Poisson and Negative Binomial models described in Section 2.2 over 2008-2023 seasons for five European soccer leagues. Negative Binomial performed considerably better across all five leagues according to both AIC and BIC criterias, demonstrating the best balance between quality of fit and simplicity. Moreover, when conducting model selection according to the procedure outlined in Section 2.3, we found that the baseline model introduced the best balance between quality of fit and complexity in vast majority of the cases. Each of the five factors was shown to be important enough to be retained in the model, while none of the interactions demonstrated a noteworthy improvement to the fit quality (for more detail, see Section 7.1). Hence, the baseline Negative Binomial model was our choice throughout the rest of the paper.

Figure 1 depicts the nature of effects for the four factors that were modeled via smoothing splines. Red card differential had a strong, nearly linear, negative impact on offensive production, while win probability difference, to the contrary, had a strong positive linear effect. When looking at the entire range of scoring differentials, it exhibited a non-linear pattern, especially on the extremes (e.g. differentials of 4 and more, in either direction). Nonetheless, for the most typically occurring score differentials (e.g. -2 to 2, as marked via dashed vertical lines) one can observe the decrease in offensive production as the difference becomes more positive. Moreover, the game minute plot effect plot indicates a notable increase in offensive production over the first 15 minutes of the game, followed by a wavy pattern of activity the rest of the game (albeit at a relatively stable level). The inconsistent pattern past the 90th minute - the extra time - is most likely attributable to smaller sample sizes of available data, given that games tend to finish shortly after 90th minute. Lastly, although not depicted on the figure, playing at home was found to

Figure 1: Nature of effects for score differential, red card differential, win probability differential and game minute on shot attempts (left) and corner kicks (right) in the final selected model fitted to 15 seasons (2008-2023) across five major European soccer leagues.

have a small positive impact on offensive production.

3.2 Statistical Adjustment

Figure 2 illustrates the multiplicative coefficients for shot attempts that result from converting effect estimates from Figure 1 according to the approach described in Section 2.3. On the example of Premier League, we see the shots generated while trailing get less credit (multiplied by 0.87-0.92, hence reduced by 8-13%), while shots produced when ahead in score are granted more weight (multiplied by 1.14-1.25, hence increased by 14-25%) when projecting onto the shared scenario of a tied game. In the meantime, shots taken while having more men (negative red card differential) are discredited at an even heavier rate (multiplied by 0.60-0.74, hence reduced by 26-40%), while shot attempts with fewer men are given plenty of extra credit (multiplied by 1.70-2.73, hence increased by 70-173%). Those patterns are quite consistent across all five leagues.

Table 1 illustrates the largest positive and largest negative adjustments to shot production in each of the five considered European soccer leagues, along with the contextual breakdown of game situations during which the shots were accumulated.

	Premier League	Ligue 1	La Liga	Serie A	Bundesliga
Score Diff = -3	0.92	0.73	0.79	0.82	0.89
Score Diff = -2	0.87	0.77	0.82	0.84	0.88
Score Diff = -1	0.89	0.84	0.86	0.87	0.88
Score Diff = 0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Score Diff = +1	1.14	1.25	1.22	1.21	1.20
Score Diff = +2	1.23	1.41	1.36	1.33	1.33
Score Diff = +3	1.25	1.43	1.34	1.32	1.33

	Premier League	Ligue 1	La Liga	Serie A	Bundesliga
RedCard Diff = -2	0.60	0.57	0.56	0.54	0.41
RedCard Diff = -1	0.74	0.70	0.71	0.70	0.66
RedCard Diff = 0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
RedCard Diff = +1	1.70	1.63	1.56	1.69	1.75
RedCard Diff = +2	2.73	2.51	2.45	2.98	2.33

Figure 2: Multiplicative coefficients for shot attempts generated during respective score (top) and red card (bottom) differentials to project it on the scenario of a tied game with equal number of men.

League	Team	Opponent	Season	Total Shots		Actual Shots (& Minutes Played) When			
				Actual	Adjusted	Up 1+ goal	Down 1+ goal	Up 1+ men	Down 1+ men
ENG	Arsenal	Everton	2016/17	17	34.7 (↑ 17.7)	15* (91)	0 (0)	0 (0)	15 (85)
ESP	Real Madrid	@ Espanyol	2010/11	18	35.3 (↑ 17.3)	13 (66)	0 (0)	0 (0)	18 (89)
FRA	Caen	@ Troyes	2015/16	15	26.3 (↑ 11.3)	13* (78)	0 (0)	0 (0)	9 (38)
GER	Bayern Mun	Stuttgart	2020/21	15	27.9 (↑ 12.9)	12* (76)	0 (0)	0 (0)	14* (82)
ITA	AS Roma	Chievo V	2009/10	17	32.9 (↑ 15.9)	15 (90)	0 (0)	0 (0)	13 (80)
...
ENG	Blackpool	W Brom	2010/11	26	12.4 (↓ 13.6)	25* (79)	0 (0)	26* (81)	0 (0)
ESP	Getafe	Deportivo	2009/10	22	11.8 (↓ 10.2)	0 (0)	22* (79)	19* (66)	0 (0)
FRA	Bordeaux	Montpellier	2021/22	31	13.6 (↓ 17.4)	0 (0)	31* (94)	31* (66)	0 (0)
GER	Eintracht	Stuttgart	2010/11	30	21.5 (↓ 8.5)	0 (0)	12* (26)	26 (76)	0 (0)
ITA	AS Roma	Venezia	2021/22	43	26.7 (↓ 16.3)	0 (0)	29 (79)	38 (70)	0 (0)

Table 1: The largest positive (top five rows) and negative (bottom five rows) adjustments to shots produced in a game in each major European soccer league. "@" indicates that the team played at the opponent's home field (hence away). "*" indicates that the game had periods with a score or red card difference of more than just ± 1 (e.g. a team was up at least 2 goals, or down 2 men).

From the five largest positive adjustments it's clear that the majority of shots were accumulated when the respective team was down at least 1 man, and mostly when up at least 1 goal (both situations are less conducive to shot production, hence they benefit from the adjustment). The largest jump happened for Arsenal in English Premier League, going from 17 shots to 34.7 after the adjustment. Vast majority of their shots (15) came when they were down 1 man (got a red card on 13th minute) and up at least 1 goal (went up 1-0 on 7th minute), both aspects being less conducive to generating offensive production. Moreover, although it's not reflected in the table, if we look at the Arsenal's opponent in that game - Everton - their 22 actual shots got projected down to 13. All of their shots took place when down at least 1 goal, and they attempted only 1 shot at even strength (before Arsenal got their red card), resulting in such a considerable downgrade. Therefore, if one were to simply look at Everton's 22 shot attempts against Arsenal's 17, they could come away thinking that Everton played more dominantly, despite having lost 1-3. With our contextual adjustment, Arsenal's impressive effort in that game (playing most of it down 1 man and in the lead) gets fully recognized, and is more in line with the eventual game outcome (Arsenal winning by 2 goals).

In regards to the five largest negative adjustments (last five rows), conversely, the majority of shots by those teams were attempted when up at least 1 man and by at least 1 goal (situations that typically result in higher shot production, hence the adjustment pulls those numbers down). The largest drop occurred for Bordeaux in French Ligue 1, where their 31 actual shots got projected down to 13.6. They went down 2 goals by 17th minute, combined with their opponent getting red cards on 39th and 45th minutes. Curiously, Bordeaux didn't attempt a single of their 31 actual shots until they started playing 11 vs 9 men which, in combination with being down 0 - 2 in score, resulted in such a huge contextual adjustment.

Lastly, although home factor was shown to have a smaller effect compared to score and red card differentials, it still contributed to the away teams getting extra credit and home teams getting adjusted down. Some of it can be seen in the fact that all five largest negative adjustments happened to teams playing at home. For the five largest positive adjustments, the home factor likely gets overshadowed by score and red card differentials.

Table 6 in the appendix presents analogous five largest positive and five largest negative adjustments for corners, and the findings are similar in that the teams getting most of their corner shots when up at least 1 man and/or at least 1 goal get adjusted down, and vice versa.

4 Conclusion & Future Work

We have modeled teams' offensive production, such as shot attempts and corner kicks, as a function of various factors that contribute to implementation of certain tactics. We found that the model yielding the best balance between quality of fit and interpretability was achieved by additive Negative Binomial regression with the baseline set of five factors: score differential, red card differential, home factor, win probability difference, and game minute. That illustrated two aspects: each of the five factors was important enough to be retained in the model, and no pairwise factor interactions were found significant enough to be included in the model. The latter presents a curious finding, as the intuition would imply potential interactions between score differential and game minute (trailing team becoming more desperate and offensively-minded as the time expires, vice versa for leading team), win probability and score or red card differentials (an inherently better team being less likely to get affected by game context and keep producing offensive output at a similar rate), among others.

As for the nature of the effects, those were all quite intuitive. Besides the non-linear and unstable nature of score differential's impact on offensive outputs in the extreme scenarios (e.g. score difference of 4+), which can be attributed to lower sample sizes and less trivial game dynamics at that point, we can observe a predictable decreasing pattern as goal differential goes from -3 to 3. Of even larger magnitude is the impact of red cards, exhibiting a strong negative trend as the red card differential increases (hence the team has fewer men). Those findings confirmed the intuition of teams with leads and/or fewer men on the field tending to play more defensively. Leading teams typically choose to do so in order to protect the lead and secure the valuable 3 points (as opposed to 1 point for a draw), while the teams with at least 1 man down are virtually forced into playing that style due to being outnumbered. Moreover, home factor has consistently showed a positive effect on team's production, albeit of relatively low magnitude. Prematch win probability differential always had a strong positive association with the offensive production, confirming the intuition of better teams (with higher betting odds) outperforming the opponent. Lastly, game minute showed a somewhat non-trivial dynamic. The clear increase of offensive production over the first 15 minutes could be attributed to teams calibrating their offenses early in the game, but the wavy pattern that follows isn't as easily explained (besides the extra time that starts past the 90th minute, where the obvious culprit is the inconsistency of sample size and data availability) and could be subject to future study. Note that these smoothing splines were estimated separately for each league via cross-validation, hence the resulting degrees of freedom were data-driven, and the pattern has repeated itself throughout all five leagues. Controlling for both the win probability differential and game minute aspects allowed for more precisely estimating the effects of factors we ended up adjusting for - score differential, red cards, and home indicator. The aforementioned results were replicated across all five major European soccer leagues and both statistical categories considered (shot attempts and corners).

When applying the statistical adjustment, we projected each team's offensive performance in a chosen statistical category onto a tied home game with equal amount of men on the field. That resulted in projecting upwards the statistics accumulated during time periods when a team was in the lead and/or down at least 1 man (to adjust for the context that's less conducive to offensive output production), and vice versa. Therefore, the largest impacts were to games with prolonged periods of imbalanced play (e.g. 9 or 10 men versus 11) and/or one team staying in the lead. Home factor played some role as well, but not to the extent of the score and red card differential.

One avenue for future work would be to model the actual quality of shot attempts generated during various game context, because clearly not all shots are equally likely to pose a true threat to the opponent. For that, our plan is to incorporate the expected goals (xG) [3] associated with each shot attempt, hereby analyzing how the quality of created scoring opportunities depends on the game context, with a potential for subsequent statistical adjustment. Also, despite us mentioning a World Cup elimination game as an illustration, note that the current work focused on national club leagues where there's no concept of elimination games, and there's clear point denomination for each outcome (3 points for a win, 1 for a draw, 0 for a loss). An obvious extension would be to study the dynamics of competitions where, instead of points, the format is more reliant upon binary game outcome (won/lost) or score differential as a way to determine who proceeds to the next round. Examples include Football Association Challenge Cup (FA Cup), World Cup or Champions League elimination stages, among others.

5 Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to New College of Florida for providing summer research funding.

6 Declaration of interest statement

Authors of this work confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest to disclose.

7 Appendix

7.1 Model comparison, detailed results

With the baseline model for shot attempts as the response looking as follows:

$$\text{Shots} \sim s(\text{Score.Diff}) + s(\text{RedCard.Diff}) + \text{HomeAway} + s(\text{Win.Prob.Diff}) + s(\text{game.minute}),$$

where s stands for smoothing splines, we consider excluding individual predictors and adding two-predictor interaction terms (via two-dimensional smoothing splines) to gauge their respective importance. Tables 2 and 3 describe the BIC and AIC results for shots as the response. The analysis for corner kicks as the response is analogous, with the results contained in Tables 4 and 5.

Model	Bundesliga	Serie A	La Liga	League 1	Premier League
Baseline	685933.3	802637.4	695665.7	778826.6	706149.8
$-s(\text{Score.Diff})$	686894.8	805774.6	697628.2	780675.1	707601.4
$-s(\text{RedCard.Diff})$	686682	803961.9	696860.8	780448.8	707198.8
$-s(\text{HomeAway})$	685983	802653	695867.9	778905.8	706207.9
$-s(\text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	689694.1	808434.8	699335.7	781794.6	712047.7
$-s(\text{game.minute})$	687715	804539.3	697234.5	780514.7	707832.6
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{RedCard.Diff})$	686017	802751	695784.1	778921.8	706259.8
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	686005.1	802747.2	695772.6	778885.4	706230.1
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	686461.3	803432.3	696218	779448.1	706657.5
$+s(\text{RedCard.Diff}, \text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	685965.4	802662.5	695698	778862.8	706142.9
$+s(\text{RedCard.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	686474.9	803479.1	696211.3	779486.8	706706.3
$+s(\text{Win.Prob.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	686505.2	803506.3	696246.9	779489.3	706708.8

Table 2: Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) values for model comparisons in predicting shot attempts. Best performing model for each respective lead is marked in **bold**. $s()$ stands for a smoothing spline term.

Model	Bundesliga	Serie A	La Liga	League 1	Premier League
Baseline	685616.5	802291.2	695331.3	778476.4	705783.1
$-s(\text{Score.Diff})$	686653.1	805527.6	697387.9	780445.2	707328.7
$-s(\text{RedCard.Diff})$	686400.2	803658.4	696561.1	780135	706875.6
$-s(\text{HomeAway})$	685676.3	802317	695534.5	778558.7	705849.7
$-s(\text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	689440.7	808168.3	699076.6	781513.4	711774.2
$-s(\text{game.minute})$	687492.8	804302.5	697001.8	780301.7	707598.4
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{RedCard.Diff})$	685667.5	802367.9	695411.4	778559.8	705865.1
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	685662.1	802383.9	695415	778560	705863.2
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	686124.1	803051.5	695864.9	779090.3	706280.5
$+s(\text{RedCard.Diff}, \text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	685616.1	802297.9	695332.7	778472.8	705773.1
$+s(\text{RedCard.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	686158.8	803123.1	695875.2	779126.4	706318.3
$+s(\text{Win.Prob.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	686140.5	803121.6	695870.4	779123.7	706308.8

Table 3: Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) values for model comparisons in predicting shot attempts. Best performing model for each respective lead is marked in **bold**. $s()$ stands for a smoothing spline term.

Model	Bundesliga	Serie A	La Liga	League 1	Premier League
Baseline	340392.7	408676.3	369503.7	401179.7	372823.4
$-s(\text{Score.Diff})$	341259.7	410960.1	371160.1	403003.3	373970.9
$-s(\text{RedCard.Diff})$	340649	409050.8	369897.6	401719.5	373156.3
$-s(\text{HomeAway})$	340405.9	408698.4	369708.1	401244.9	372847.7
$-s(\text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	342251.5	411192.4	371155.8	402594.9	375552.5
$-s(\text{game.minute})$	340687.7	409015.7	369747.9	401537.3	373182.8
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{RedCard.Diff})$	340472.1	408760.8	369620.6	401270.4	372928.3
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	340459.2	408764.3	369617.1	401262.9	372871.6
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	340632.1	408964.3	369745.6	401465.9	373048.4
$+s(\text{RedCard.Diff}, \text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	340431.1	408693	369525.7	401207.4	372801.3
$+s(\text{RedCard.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	340584.9	408930.5	369677.4	401427.4	373008.1
$+s(\text{Win.Prob.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	340614.7	408951.7	369660.7	401437.1	373005.3

Table 4: Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) values for model comparisons in predicting corner kicks. Best performing model for each respective lead is marked in **bold**. $s()$ stands for a smoothing spline term.

Model	Bundesliga	Serie A	La Liga	League 1	Premier League
Baseline	340076.5	408343.6	369210.8	400861	372471.4
$-s(\text{Score.Diff})$	341021.3	410716.8	370978	402769	373742.4
$-s(\text{RedCard.Diff})$	340363.8	408761.9	369642.1	401436.1	372839.5
$-s(\text{HomeAway})$	340099	408374.1	369389.6	400935.4	372507.9
$-s(\text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	342006.7	410934.7	370908.1	402344.6	375308.7
$-s(\text{game.minute})$	340471.2	408789.4	369564	401329.5	372938.6
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{RedCard.Diff})$	340138.7	408392.7	369304.7	400929.8	372555.9
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	340119.5	408411.7	369270.7	400922.8	372548.2
$+s(\text{Score.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	340309.2	408636.2	369466.1	401154	372702.1
$+s(\text{RedCard.Diff}, \text{Win.Prob.Diff})$	340082.6	408344.4	369208.6	400865.2	372479.8
$+s(\text{RedCard.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	340279.2	408607.7	369392.3	401113.3	372653.4
$+s(\text{Win.Prob.Diff}, \text{game.minute})$	340280.1	408595.5	369370.4	401128.4	372666.1

Table 5: Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) values for model comparisons in predicting corner kicks. Best performing model for each respective lead is marked in **bold**. $s()$ stands for a smoothing spline term.

Main takeaway is that the baseline model outperforms (or is at least on par with) all the modified models in vast majority of cases. It yielded the best BIC values in both shots and corner kicks for 4 out of 5 leagues - all but the Premier League, where it was second only to the interaction between red card and win probability differential. In regards to AIC values, baseline was the best in regards to shot attempts for two leagues, and was on par or just behind the interaction between red card and win probability differential in the other three. AIC values for corner kicks showed baseline model as the best in 4 out of 5 leagues - all but La Liga, where it came second to the interaction between red card and win probability differential. All-in-all, there wasn't enough evidence across all comparisons that any model managed to consistently outperform the baseline.

7.2 Statistical Adjustment: Corner Kicks

League	Team	Opponent	Season	Total Corners		Actual Corners (& Minutes Played) When			
				Actual	Adjusted	Up 1+ goal	Down 1+ goal	Up 1+ men	Down 1+ men
ENG	Man City	@ Norwich	2012/13	9	16.7 (↑ 7.7)	9*(101)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (59)
ESP	Barcelona	@ Celta	2020/21	8	21.6 (↑ 13.6)	8*(91)	0 (0)	0 (0)	7 (60)
FRA	Marseille	@ Guingamp	2017/18	11	18 (↑ 7.0)	2*(53)	0 (11)	0 (0)	8 (31)
GER	Wolfsburg	@ Eintracht	2012/13	9	16.9 (↑ 7.9)	8*(87)	0 (0)	0 (0)	7 (62)
ITA	AS Roma	Palermo	2012/13	15	25.2 (↑ 10.2)	13*(85)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (14)
...
ENG	Bournemouth	Tottenham	2018/19	10	5.6 (↓ 4.4)	0 (5)	0 (0)	9*(58)	0 (0)
ESP	Getafe	Deportivo	2009/10	14	9.2 (↓ 4.8)	0 (0)	13*(79)	11*(66)	0 (0)
FRA	Paris St-Ger	St Rennais	2012/13	18	9.1 (↓ 8.9)	0 (0)	17 (71)	16*(72)	0 (0)
GER	Eintracht	Stuttgart	2010/11	13	8.7 (↓ 4.3)	0 (0)	5*(26)	13 (76)	0 (0)
ITA	AS Roma	Venezia	2021/22	20	12.5 (↓ 7.5)	0 (0)	14 (79)	18 (70)	0 (0)

Table 6: The largest positive (top five rows) and negative (bottom five rows) adjustments to corner kicks produced in a game in each major European soccer league. ”@” indicates that team played at opponent’s home field (hence away). ”*” indicates that the game had periods with a score or red card difference of more than just ± 1 (e.g. a team was up at least 2 goals, or down 2 men)

References

- [1] One month on: 5 billion engaged with the FIFA world cup qatar 2022™.
- [2] Espn: France 2-1 england (dec 10, 2022) commentary.
- [3] Jonny Whitmore. What is expected goals?
- [4] James Mead, Anthony O’Hare, and Paul McMenemy. Expected goals in football: Improving model performance and demonstrating value. 18(4):e0282295. Publisher: Public Library of Science.
- [5] Ben Baldwin. Open source football: nflfastr ep, wp, cp xyac, and xpass models, 2021.
- [6] Thomas Kempton, Nicholas Kennedy, and Aaron J Coutts. The expected value of possession in professional rugby league match-play. *Journal of sports sciences*, 34(7):645–650, 2016.
- [7] Dimitris Karlis and Ioannis Ntzoufras. Analysis of sports data by using bivariate poisson models. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series D (The Statistician)*, 52(3):381–393, 2003.
- [8] Georgi Boshnakov, Tarak Kharrat, and Ian G McHale. A bivariate weibull count model for forecasting association football scores. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 33(2):458–466, 2017.
- [9] David Harville. The use of linear-model methodology to rate high school or college football teams. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 72(358):278–289, 1977.
- [10] Anjela Y Govan, Amy N Langville, and Carl D Meyer. Offense-defense approach to ranking team sports. *Journal of Quantitative Analysis in Sports*, 5(1), 2009.
- [11] Andrey Skripnikov. Partially constrained group variable selection to adjust for complemen-

- tary unit performance in american college football. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, pages 1–15, 2023.
- [12] John Edwards and Denise Archambault. The home field advantage. *Sports, games, and play: Social and psychological viewpoints*, pages 409–438, 1979.
- [13] The selenium browser automation documentation.
- [14] Frank A Haight. Handbook of the poisson distribution. (*No Title*), 1967.
- [15] Peter McCullagh. *Generalized linear models*. Routledge, 2019.
- [16] Simon N Wood. *Generalized additive models: an introduction with R*. chapman and hall/CRC, 2017.
- [17] Gareth James, Daniela Witten, Trevor Hastie, Robert Tibshirani, et al. *An introduction to statistical learning*, volume 112. Springer, 2013.